

DARUHARIDRA, GUGGUL, AND TRIKATU: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW THEIR EFFICACY IN COMBATING CHOLESTEROL, HYPERLIPIDEMIA, AND OBESITY

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Hyperlipidemia as a problem

In India, non-communicable diseases (NCDs) are the leading cause of death, accounting for 63% of all deaths, according to WHO's 2018 NCD India profile. Cardiovascular diseases (27%), chronic respiratory diseases (11%), cancers (9%), diabetes (3%), and **obesity (13%)** are the other leading causes.

Hyper- lipidemia is a health condition which results in the chronic elevation of cholesterol, triglycerides and phospholipids. Due to this elevated lipids content in the blood it will get deposited in the walls of arteries. This acts as a precursor for many hazardous health dis- eases such as Atherosclerosis, heart attack, strokes, etc. Overall deaths due to elevated levels of cholesterol are found to be 2.6mil- lion deaths and 29.7 million disabilities. The food source of cholesterol are from high-fat dairy products like milk, cream,

yogurt, butter and ghee, etc. Cholesterol comprises two types: low-den- sitylipoproteins (LDL) and high- density lipoproteins (HDL). LDL is known as 'bad' cholesterol and can cause conditions like strokes, carotid artery disease, and peripheral arterial disease.

HDL, on the other hand, is called ‘good’ cholesterol and helps remove LDL from the body. Any imbalance in these levels can lead to hyperlipidemia. The increasing prevalence of overweight and obesity among children and adolescents is a major global public health issue. In 1990, the rates for children aged 5–19 were 8% and 2%,. However, by 2022, these rates had increases to 20% and 8%, respectively. Overweight and obesity, once considered public health concerns in high-income countries, are now rapidly becoming serious health problems across age groups, including children and adolescents in low and middle-income countries. The root causes of obesity and dyslipidemia are excess junk food consumption, low physical activities and neglected self-care. India has the world’s largest adolescent population with 253 million adolescents India in the last couple of decades transitioned from a high adolescent undernutrition-burdened state to a scenario with rapidly rising adolescence-associated incidences of overweight and obesity. And India is the world’s largest adolescent population with 253 million adolescents.^[1,2,3]

Lipoproteins	Normal range	Risk condition
LDL	Under 100 mg/dl	160 and high
HDL	Greater than 60 mg/dl	Under 40-50 mg/dl
VLDL	2 and 30 mg/dl	Above 30 mg/dl
Triglycerides	Less than 150 mg/dl	Above 200 mg/dl
Total	Under 200 mg/dl	240 mg/dl and higher

2. MECHANISM OF ACTION

Hyperlipidemia is defines as high cholesterol and triglycerides levels in blood stream due to genetic or diet related issue. Improper LDL receptor activity and elevated PCSK9 expression gives rise to cholesterol accumulation. Deficiency of lipoprotein lipase (LPL) activity will results in high triglyceride levels. In Addition to that, Oxidation of LDL will contributes to vascular inflammation and atherosclerosis. To counter hyperlipidemia there are certain

pathways like.

• 2.1-BY ACTIVATING ERK AND JNK PATHWAYS^[4,5,6]

By activating ERK and JNK signalling pathways, which directly activate the LDL receptor gene (LDLR). This process occurs through a post-transcriptional mechanism that enhances both the production and stability of LDL receptor.

• 2.3 – BY ENHANCING THERMOGENESIS

Inducing thermogenesis mechanism directly targets the fat-burning systems of the body to decrease hyperlipidemia. The main bioactive compounds responsible for this effect are gingerol and shogaol, which contain a vanillyl moiety. This moiety enables activation of TRPV1, a receptor activated by ginger. Upon activation of TRPV1, further stimulate the production of catecholamines, such as adrenaline and noradrenaline. These catecholamines then activate brown adipose tissue and promote the browning of white adipose tissue. This process significantly upregulates UCP1 (uncoupling protein 1), the key thermogenic protein that uncouples oxidative phosphorylation in mitochondria. This uncoupling process causes energy to be released as heat rather than stored as ATP.

• 2.4 - BY MODULATION OF MELANOCORTIN-4 RECEPTOR

The **melanocortin-4 receptor (MC4R)** is a key component of the body's weight regulation system. Located primarily in the **hypothalamus**, this receptor acts as a central switch that, when activated, promotes a negative feedback which means more calories are burned than it consumed. This process is carried out by **α -MSH**. When a person having satisfied in a petite the, POMC(**proopiomelanocortin**) neurons releases of α -MSH, which then binds and activating the MC4R. This activation leads to two primary responses: it suppresses feelings of hunger and increases feeling like **satiety** (the feeling of fullness), also it stimulates the **sympathetic nervous system** and order to increase energy expenditure, helps to boost heat production (**thermogenesis**) in tissues like **brown adipose tissue**.

3 Daruharidra (*Berberine aristata*)^[10,11,12,13,14,15]

Berberis aristata popularly known as daruharidra, is a widely used as a traditional medicine systems worldwide for centuries that including Ayurveda, Homeopathy, Unani, Chinese, and Allopathy, and it is officially recognised in the Ayurvedic and Siddha Pharmacopoeia of India. Each component of these plant like its active ingredients berberine, has gained significance recognition due to its diverse medicinal uses. It belongs to the Berberidaceae family which has many common or folks name like, Daru Haldi, Indian barberry, Tree turmeric, and Chitra. Daruharidra or berberin Primarily grown and cultivated in the sub-Himalayan region of southern India and hilly areas of Nepal and approximately 77 of the over 500 pharmacologically relevant species in the genus *Berberis* are native to India. Berberin arista roots are considered to be the official source of drug that is Berberin and it is the primary alkaloid component which is found in the plant's leaves, roots, rhizomes, and stem bark. Some research studies have shown that the stem and root parts of *Berberis aristata* are commonly sold as the name Daruharidra in India. As the

research conducts the first reported to have hypoglycemic activity is noted in 1988 when it was prescribed to treat diarrhoea and diabetic patients. *Berberis aristata* which is an important and life saving herb in numerous traditional medical systems because it shows various therapeutic properties listed below that includes antibacterial, antiamoebic, antifungal, antihelminthic and anti-inflammatory effects most importantly It also inhibits smooth muscle contraction, bacterial enterotoxin formation, platelet aggregation additionally stimulates bile and bilirubin secretion. **Medicinal Properties:** Anti-diabetic, anti-microbial, anti-cancer, antilipidemic, antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, anti-diarrheal, hepatoprotective and cardiogenic effects.

3.1 Mechanism of *Berberis aristata*

Berberine is an isoquinoline derivative alkaloid isolated from many kinds of medicinal herbs, such as *Hydrastis canadensis* (goldenseal), *Cortex Phellodendri* (Huangbai), and *Rhizoma Coptidis* (Huanglian). Leptin and adiponectin are the key biomarkers of adipose tissue. Hyperleptinemia and hypoadiponectinemia are common in obesity. They reflect increased adiposity and contribute to, dyslipidemia. Zhang et al. also found berberine-moderated glucose and lipid metabolism through a multi-pathway mechanism that includes AMP-activated protein kinase- (AMPK-) p38 MAPK-GLUT4, JNK pathway, and PPAR α pathway *Berberis aristata* increases the number of LDL receptors in the body, which helps remove bad cholesterol from the blood. It does this without using the usual cholesterol-controlling proteins (SREBPs), and instead relies on special signaling pathways called ERK and JNK. The hypolipidemic effects of *B. aristata* may be due to the presence of berberine, oxyacanthine, berbamine and palmatine.

3.2- Pharmacognosy of *Berberis aristata*

○ Synonyms and Common names

- *Indian barberry*
- *Tree turmeric*
- *Daru haldi*
- *Mara manjal*

○ Biological Source

- Dried roots and stem bark of *Berberis aristata* [daruharidra]

○ Family

- Berberidaceae

○ Taxonomy of *Berberis aristata*

- *Kingdom: Plantae*
- *Division: Magnoliophyta*
- *Class: Magnoliopsida*
- *Order: Ranunculales*
- *Family: Berberidaceae*
- *Genus: Berberis*
- *Species: aristata.*

Plant Part	Phytochemical Type	Specific Compounds
Root Bark	Alkaloids	Chalasin, Aromarin, Oxyberberine, Oxyacanthine,
Flowers	Flavonoids	Quercetin, Rutin, Melanin
Flowers	Acids	Caffeic acid, Chlorogenic acid
Bark	Alkaloids	Pakistanine, 1-O-methyl pakistanine, Pseudopalmitine
Bark	Alkaloid	Taxylamine
Powdered Skin	Alkaloids	Berberine, Tetrahydropalmitine, Tetrahydroberberine,
Heartwood	Hydrocarbon	n-docosan
Root	Alkaloids	L-Tyrosine, Dopamine, p-hydroxyphenylacetaldehyde, Norcoclaurin, N-methylcoclaurin, Coclaurin, Oxyacanthine, Aromarin, Berbamin, 3'-hydroxy-N-methylcoclaurin, 3'-

3.3- Biological Applications

○ Antihyperglycemic Activity

Ethanol extracts from *B. arisata* effectively reduced serum glucose levels in both normal and diabetic rats, reporting potential as an adjunct to insulin. The extract compound hypoglycemic effects were greater than glibenclamide additionally it also reducing triglycerides and cholesterol levels plus it also improves HDL levels.

○ Hepatoprotective activity

A study in golden hamsters reported that *B. aristata* reduced hepatic amoebiasis infection in rates claiming that it protected rats from liver damage and is effective against liver fibrosis.

Species/Part	Alkaloid Content	Notes
Various <i>Berberis</i> species	Berberine, berbamine, palmitine, jatrorrhizine, isotetrandrine	Most common alkaloids
Roots and stems	High berberine concentration	Cortical tissues of roots and stems
Old root bark	Highest berberine concentration	Upper stem parts have low concentrations, young leaves lack them
Indian <i>Berberis</i> species	Berberine, umbellatine, nepiotime	Histological distribution studied
Young shoots	0.04% berberine	Average content
Young parenchymatous roots	1.41% berberine	Content increases with plant age
Rasaut (traditional Punjab market preparation)	1.67-4.26% total alkaloids	Chemical analysis
<i>B. lycium</i>	15.4% w/v total alkaloids, 9.4% w/v berberine	Yield and berberine content

○ Antimicrobial activity

Berberine extract from the plant showed effective result at anti-microbial activity against various microbes like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Corynebacterium*. The herbal gel containing *B. aristata* extract was effective against skin infections observed in a study.

○ Anti-diabetic activity

Practical performed studies showed that the ethanolic extract of *B. aristata* has anti-diabetic activity in alloxan-induced diabetic rats as it inhibits DPP-IV receptor which shows potential anti-diabetic properties.

4. Guggul (*Commiphora mukul*)^[16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25]

A popular Ayurvedic herb Guggul is derived from *Commiphora wightii*, which is native to India. Moreover, *C. wightii* grows wild in various states, including Rajasthan, Gujarat, Karnataka, and parts of Afghanistan, Arabia, and northeast Africa. It is a thorny shrub with ash-coloured bark that flakes out easily. Guggul is a resin from the *C. mukul* plant which has been used medicinally for its disease-repelling properties over a long period of time. It is traditionally used in yoga and has been reported results such as to reduce fat and heal various diseases. The National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) nominated gum guggul extract for toxicological characterisation due to its increasing demand as a dietary supplement and the lack of information on safe human use. Its effects on lipid metabolism, thyroid hormone homeostasis, female reproductive tissues, endogenous nuclear hormone receptors, and potential drug interactions approve further study.

The chemical investigations aimed to isolate the compounds in the oleo-gum resin of *C. wightii* responsible for its hypocholesterolaemic/hypolipaeamic activity. The chemistry team at

the National Chemical Laboratory, Pune, and later at the Multi-Chem Research Centre, Vadodara, developed a viable separation scheme.

4.1 Mechanism of Guggul

Guggul is a Oleo-gum resin which obtained from the stem branches of *Commiphora Mukul* including, *Balsamodendron mukul* which is native to India, it has been widely utilised in Ayurveda for over 3,000 years due to its lot of benefits. it belongs to the *Burser-aceae* family which contains bioactive compounds such as guggulsterone, and is frequently used in the reduction of cholesterol levels, alleviate arthritis, manage weight, and enhance cardiovascular health. Some Research indicates that guggulsterone isomers increases the bile salt export pump (BSEP), an efflux transporter responsible for the excretion of cholesterol metabolites and bile acids from the liver. E-guggulsterone, specifically 16-dehydropregnenolone acetate, exhibits enhanced lipid-lowering activity by inhibiting the Farnesoid X receptor. It has been seen that many dietary supplement are available in the US and INDIA which assures to reduce LDL cholesterol, triglycerides, and inhibit platelet aggregation by showing antagonistic effect on the nuclear receptors farnesoid X receptor (FXR) and bile acid receptor (BAR), which are involved in cholesterol metabolism and bile acid regulation. These supplement containing guggul can also slows down liver ability to make certain fats and cholesterol by inhibiting HMG-CoA reductase it also activate the thyroid gland, which boosts metabolism and indirectly reduces cholesterol levels.

4.2 Pharmacognosy of guggul

○ Synonyms and Common names

- Hindi: Gogil, Gugal, Guggul, Mukul, Ranghanturb, Gugava, Gugavik
- Sanskrit: Bhavabhishta, Bhutahara, Devadhupa, Deveshta, Dhurta, Divya, Durga, Guggalu, Jatala, Jatayu, Kalaniriyasa, Kaushika, Kumbha, Kumlihi, Kumbholu, Kumbholu-Khalaka, Kunti, Pavandvishta, Pura, Puta, Rakshoha, Sarva-saha, Shambhava, Shiva, Uddipta, Ulukhalaka, Usha, Vayughna.
- Tamil: Gukkulu, Mai shakshi, Kukkil, Gukkal, Guggal, Gugal, Gukkula, Maishakshim, Mahishaksh-Gugilamu, Cheetu-mahishashi.
- English: Gum guggulu, Indian bdellium, Salativee, Bdellium, Guggulu, Borassaus, and Flabelliformis.
- Marathi: Guggala, Gulag, Gugal, Guggal, Guggul, Hansaguggul, Kantguggul, Mahaishguggul.
- Gujarati: Gugal, Gugali, Gugar, Guggul, Mukul, Ranghanturb, Gugul, Bhesaghala, Gugara, Ranghanturb, Bhaisoguggul
- Bengali: Gugal, Guggul, Mukul, Ranghanturb, Guggulu, Guggal, Ranghanturb, Makal, Canarese.

○ Biological Source

- obtained as an exudates from the tapping of stem and branches of *Commiphora wightii*.

○ Family

- Burseraceae

○ Taxonomical Classification of

Commiphora Mukkul

- Kingdom Plantae
- Subkingdom Tracheobionta
- Division Magnoliophyta
- Class Spermatopsida
- Sub Class Maqnoliidae
- Order Sapindales
- Genus *Commiphora*
- Species *Mukul*

○ Phytochemical constituents

S.NO.	Active constituent	There effect
1	E-Guggulsterone and Z-Guggulsterone (ketonic part)	has the property of lowering blood lipid (hypolipidemic activity)
2	Naringenin	prevents the accumulation of lipoproteins and also acts as an-
3	Cembranoid	controls the gastrointestinal absorption of cholesterol and fat.
4	Myrrhanol i.e. triterpenoid of guggul gum m	acts as antiinflammatory. and also used to reduce pain for
5	Alpha pinene	acts as anti- fungal and also anti-microbial agent.
6	Eugenol(mono terpenoid)	has the anti- oxidant property and it also plays a vital role in the
8	Alpha terpineol	has strong anti-microbial activity.
9	Beta sitostero	inhibits the cholesterol ⁴⁰ in the body and reduces the level of
10	1,8-cineole	acts as anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive ⁴¹ agent.
11	Quercetin	has the most effective inducer effect for the anticarcinogeni c
12	Diayangambin	has the immunomodula tory and antiinflammato ry activity and
13	Ellagic acid	has the anti-mutagen, anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer activity.

14	L-Arabinose	does not have any biological use but it is a good source of sugar.
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4.3- Biological Applications

○ Antihyperlipidemic activity

Guggulu was first reported to have lipid-lowering effects in 1966. research suggest that guggulsterone a mojour therapeutic compounds found in Guggulu have a property to reduce lipid levels by inhibiting the farnesoid X receptor (FXR), a key regulator of cholesterol and bile acid homeostasis. Gugulipid, a standardised extract of Guggulu, has been commercially available in India since 1988 as a hypolipidemic agent.

○ Antiatherosclerotic Activity

Guggulsterones is also the lipid-lowering components present in guggulu it potentially inhibit LDL oxidation which is a crucial factor in atherosclerosis. Ultimately makes it a effective in slowing or stopping atherogeOn0esi0s.

○ Antifertility Activity

Studies on female rats showed it reduced the weight of reproductive organs but increased glycogen and sialic acid levels.

○ Nodulocystic acne

Effective in treating nodulocystic acne and allergic dermatitis because it has anti-sebum and antioxidant properties, improving skin colour and reducing sebum secretion.

○ Antimicrobial Activity

Guggulu volatile oil and ethanol-based extracts showed strong antimicrobial properties as particularly against multidrug-resistant *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Rhizopertha dominica*.

5. Trikatu. Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), Black Pepper (*Piper nigrum*), and Long Pepper (*Piper longum*)^[26,27,28,29,30]

Trikatu is a combination of *Pippali*, *Maricha*, and *Shunti* in equal proportions which has a pungent taste (Katu rasa) and a hot potency (Ushna veerya). It has light (laghu), dry (ruksha), stimulating (deepana), and has Kapha-Vatahara properties. Trikatu also shows amapachaka (digestive) effect. The extraction compound of trikatu churna has high antibacterial activity, almost equal to the standard ampicillin solution. It also contains various and major phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, and phytosterols.

5.1 Mechanism of trikatu^[31,32]

Trikatu is a well-known Thai traditional formulation it is made of three equal parts of ginger, black pepper, and long pepper. Research studies have shown that Trikatu reduces body weight, skinfold thickness, and total cholesterol levels in obese and hypercholesterolemic patients by inhibiting alpha-glucosidases, delaying glucose absorption and reducing hyperglycaemia. It has been found that trikatu bioactive phytochemicals target 51 proteins, regulating pathways like insulin resistance and steroid hormone biosynthesis and molecular docking confirms strong interactions between key proteins and their ligands.

5.2 Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*)^[33,34,35,36,37,38]

Ginger is a flowering plant whose rhizome, or ginger root, is a key spice and has various medicinal ingredients. Anciently, it was the first spice exported from Asia to Europe and has long been valued by ancient cultures like the Greeks and Romans. The dried form of the rhizome is known as **shunti**, which is harvested in India for long time and has potent antioxidant properties additionally including free radical scavenging and lipid peroxidation inhibition, contributing to its gastroprotective effects. The active compounds in ginger, such as **gingerols**, **shogaols**, **paradol**, and **zingerone**, are responsible for many therapeutic effects. These compounds act on various biological pathways and key cell signaling mediators, offering benefits from digestive health and pain relief to cancer prevention and neurological support.

5.2.1 Pharmacognosy of Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*)

○ Synonyms and Common names

- **Sanskrit:** *Adraka* (fresh), *Shunti* (dried)
- **Hindi:** *Adrak* (fresh), *Sonth* (dried)
- **Malayalam:** *Inchi* (fresh), *Chukku* (dried)

- **Tamil:** *Ingee* (fresh), *Chukku* (dried)
- **Bengali:** *Ada*

○ Botanical source

- The biological source of ginger is the rhizome of the plant **Zingiber officinale Roscoe**

○ Family

- Zingiberaceae.

○ Taxonomical Classification of ginger

- **Kingdom:** Plantae (Plants)
- **Division (or Phylum):** Tracheophyta (Vascular plants)
- **Class:** Liliopsida (Monocots)
- **Order:** Zingiberales
- **Family:** Zingiberaceae (the ginger family)
- **Genus:** Zingiber
- **Species:** *Z. officinale*

○ Phytochemical constituents

Component Class	Components
Monoterpenoids	b-phellandrene, (+)-camphene, cineole, geraniol, curcumene, citral, terpineol, borneol
Sesquiterpenoids	a-zingiberene, b-sesquiphellandrene, b-bisabolene, (E-E)-a-farnesene, ar-curcumene, zingiberol
Gingerols	methyl ^[4] -gingerol, methyl ^[8] -gingerol
Shogaols	^[4] -, ^[6] -, ^[8] -, ^[10] -, ^[12] -shogaol
Paradol	^[6] -, ^[7] -, ^[8] -, ^[9] -, ^[10] -, ^[11] -, ^[13] -paradol, methyl ^[6] -paradol

○ Family

- Piperaceae

○ Taxonomical Classification of Piper nigrum Kingdom: Plantae

- Class: Equisetopsida
- Sub class: Magnoliidae
- Super order: Magnolianaes
- Order: Piperales
- Family: Piperaceae
- Genus: Piper
- Species: nigrum

5.3 Black Pepper (*Piper nigrum*)^[39,40,41,42]

Piper nigrum also commonly known as black pepper is a tropical vine which is valued for its medicinal properties and culinary uses. It exhibits various pharmacological activities such as antihypertensive, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects, because of its primary compound, piperine.

5.3.1 pharmacognosy of Black Pepper (*Piper nigrum*)

○ Synonyms and common names

- **Synonyms:** Pepper, black pepper, "king of spices."

○ Botanical name

- The dried unripe fruit (berry)
- Phytochemical constituents.

Compound Class	Specific Compounds
Alkaloids	Piperine, Brachyamide B, Dihydro-pipericide, (2E,4E)-N-Eicosadienoyl-piperidine, N-trans-Feruloyltryamine, N-Formylpiperidine, Guineensine, (2E,4E)-Nisobutyl-decadienamid, isobutyl-eicosadienamide, Tricholein, Trichostachine, isobutyl-eicosatrienamide, Isobutyl-octadienamide, Piperamide, Piperamine, Piperettine, Pipericide,

5.4 Long Pepper (*Piper longum*).^[43,44,45]

Piper longum Linn is a medicinal plant and commercially important for tropical and subtropical uses and is most valued for its therapeutic properties.

5.4.1 Pharmacognosy of Long Pepper (*Piper longum*)

○ Synonyms and common names

- Bengali: Pipul
- Inglese: Pepe lungo
- Gujarati: Lindi
- Hindi: Pippal, pippar
- Kannada: Hippali
- Modi: Pippali
- Malayalam: Pippali
- Marathi: Pippal
- Oriya: Pippalimula
- Punjabi: Maghan
- Tamil: Tippili
- Telugu: Pippal chettu
- Urdu: Filfil Daraz
- Sanscrito: Krishnapippali, Magadhi, Pippali, Tikshnatanduli

○ Botanical name

- *Piper longum*.

○ Family

- Piperaceae

○ Taxonomical classification of piper longum

- **Kingdom:** Plantae
- **Phylum:** Tracheophyta (Vascular plants)
- **Class:** Magnoliopsida (Dicotyledons)
- **Order:** Piperales
- **Genus:** *Piper*
- **Species:** *Piper longum*

○ Phytochemical constituents

Plant Part	Constituent	Notes
Fruits	Volatile oil, starch, protein, alkaloids,	No tannins present

	saponins, carbohydrate	
Roots	Alkaloids: piperlongum inine (0.2- 0.25%), piperlongum ine (0.02%)	Further purification yielded six known alkaloids
Spikes (Steam istillation)	Essential oil (0.7%)	Spicy odour resembling pepper and ginger oil
Plant	Alkaloids: piperine, piplartine, pipernonaline, piperundecal idine, pipericide,	Additional alkaloids identified
Seeds	Fatty acids: palmitic, hexadecenoic, stearic, linoleic,oleic, linolenic, arachidic,	Fatty acid composition

5.4 biological applications of trikatu

○ Bioavailability enhancement

enhance bioavailability of drug by modulating metabolism and transport mechanism for examole CYP inhibition.

○ Hepatoprotection

animal studies suggest hepatoprotective effect against carbon tetra chloride induced injury.

6. CONCLUSION

This review concluded that Daruharidra, Guggul, and Trikatu are been offer a practical, multi-target approach for managing high cholesterol, high triglycerides, obesity, and related metabolic risks. Together their well- studied phytoconstituent—such as berberine, guggulsterones, gingerols, shogaols, and piperine supports healthier lipid profiles, better glucose handling, and reduced inflammation through different pathways that influence cholesterol clearance, bile acid metabolism, energy expenditure, and oxidative stress. Evidence from traditional use, preclinical studies, and early clinical findings is

encouraging and suggests meaningful improvements in total cholesterol, LDL, triglycerides, HDL balance, and markers of adiposity. At the same time advancing these botanicals into routine care requires stronger clinical trials dose standardization and robust quality control to ensure safety consistency and effectiveness. By consuming together these herbs present a beneficial path.

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